

IMPACT OF FINTECH COMPANIES IN SHAPING THE FUTURE BANKING IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Fintech is ruling the world and financial sector, and it is critical to adopt the technologies that are transforming the financial sector. Fintech has altered the banking industry by providing smart services, improved customer connectivity, and value-added services; Fintech is governing the world and the financial sector, and it is critical to accept the technologies that are revolutionising the industry. Fintech was able to break into the market thanks to the rising usage of smart phones and the development of relevant tools and platforms, offering products and solutions for which banks claimed there were no substitutes, such as e-payments and online trading. Fintech in India will grow both vertically and horizontally in the future. Existing technology will become more accessible to a larger number of individuals as a result of horizontal growth. These non-banking financial enterprises are causing banks to tremble, since they now have new competitors to contend with. However, while FinTech firms are widely regarded as a huge threat to banks, they also represent a significant opportunity. In terms of a career, the bottom line is that FinTech should be viewed as a fantastic opportunity, with people with the necessary experience in high demand from banks, IT businesses, and new start-ups alike. In this three-way tug of war, the financial technology expert emerges victorious in all three scenarios. FinTech firms are currently at the forefront of the business, developing a wide range of new financial products and services aimed at making money management easier and more efficient. Asset management: Tools and technologies for data processing and analysis have boosted automation, particularly in asset rebalancing. FinTech is a Personal Capital, Lending Club, Kabbage, and Wealthfront are examples of well-known FinTech companies that have developed in the last decade, bringing fresh twists on financial principles and allowing individuals to have greater control over their financial results. Fintech and other sectors will evolve in tandem with technology. FinTech will revolutionise e-banking by offering the finest customer experience underpinned by cutting-edge technology. Furthermore, firms that wish to maintain a competitive advantage and offer the most up-to-date products will have no choice but to evolve in tandem with technology.

Keywords: Fintech, Banking, Finance, Firms, Technology.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Fintech has altered the banking industry by providing smart services, improved customer connectivity, and value-added services; Fintech is governing the world and the financial sector, and it is critical to accept the technologies that are revolutionising the industry.

Fintech was able to break into the market thanks to the rising usage of smart phones and the development of relevant tools and platforms, offering products and solutions for which banks claimed there were no substitutes, such as e-payments and online trading. Fintech in India will grow both vertically and horizontally in the future. Existing technology will become more accessible to a larger number of individuals as a result of horizontal growth.

- FinTech financial services is transforming the entire banking system from a branch-specific process to various digital channels such as online, social, and mobile.
- FinTech firms are currently at the forefront of the business, developing a wide range of new financial products and services aimed at making money management easier and more efficient.

FinTech will revolution is e-banking by offering the finest customer experience underpinned by cutting-edge technology.

2. Related Works :

Below Table 1 shows systematic literature of review is conducted from 2017 to 2022 by using the keywords “Fin-Tech Banks”, “ Fin- Tech Companies “ from google scholar and research gate.

Table 1: Related works on Fintech

S. No	Focus	Outcome	Reference
1.	FinTech firms engaging in banking service spaces have led to a disintermediation of incumbent banks, partly benefiting from the current lenient regulation.	The rise of FinTech and the path to digital transformation.	Murinde, V., Rizopoulos, E., & Zachariadis, M (2022). [1]
2.	The Reserve Bank has over the years encouraged greater use of electronic payments so as to achieve a ‘less-cash’ society.	Digital onboarding and financial inclusion	Das, S. (2019). [2]

3.	Analyses the major transformational points in the Indian Banking Industry and the current level of banking in India.	The banking sector is under threat due to the disruption caused by Fintech companies.	Jadwani, B [3]
4.	Fintech has been applied to increase inclusive financial development in Kenya, India and China.	The cases have been selected based on how effectively Fintech services were adopted in each country to create an inclusive financial environment.	Guild, J. (2017).[4]
5.	Financial Technology sector in India is expanding fast with an innovation driven start up, huge market base, favorable regulations and government policies.	This research paper traces the various risk management challenges and opportunities that Indian Banking System is facing in collaboration and co invention with Fintech firms.	Bhasin, N. K., & Rajesh, A. (2021) [5]
6.	Some of fintech’s most important “huge stuff” is the rise of the mobile payment industry.	Fintech developments caused a change in conventional paradigms in financial services and led major financial companies to reassess how they do business.	Kukreja, G., Bahl, D., & Gupta, R. (2021)[6]

3. OBJECTIVES:

- a) To study the various Fintech innovations, new products, E Collaboration and delivery channels adopted by Indian Banks and Financial Institutions.
- b) To examine and analyze the impact of Fintech Investments and E Collaborations on adoption of new technology driven products by banks and its customer.
- c) To compare and contrast the various digital and Fintech collaboration.
- d) To analyze the emerging trends and impact of the Fintech revolution on the banking sector in India.

4. METHODOLOGY:

Secondary Data has been collected, studied and analyzed from the various sources as mentioned below:

- a. Research Journal and Papers

- b. Websites of Banks, Financial Institutions and Fintech
- c. Newspaper Articles
- d. Published Reports

5. BENEFITS OF FINTECH:

A) CUSTOMER SERVICES AND REVENUE:

By increased productivity and efficiency, fintech raises the standard of traditional financial institutions. More chances develop if fintech companies are seen by banks and credit unions as allies rather than competitors. Additionally, by offering better and more modern services, businesses' client retention rates are bound to increase, leading to higher revenues.

B) REDUCED COSTS:

You might assume that using cutting-edge technologies will cost you a fortune, but this isn't always the case. The financial technology corporations have limits on how much money they can spend on technology. With financial technology, however, that is not the case; instead, they would help to bring down overall expenses. Fintech has been used to combine physical and digital payments into a single platform by combining bank accounts, credit cards, and client identification. The primary factor in favour of enterprises is how they provide practical transaction possibilities within a constrained budget.

C) GREATER CONVENIENCE:

Financial services are more about providing convenience than spending money, as we said at the outset. The most practical approach to run a banking firm is through the use of fintech software in businesses. Because Fintech leverages technology to provide users with a better and more dependable customer experience, businesses are embracing it. Blockchain, AI, IoT, machine learning, and several more financial technologies that will help them in the long term are the technologies that are improving the financial businesses.

D) SPEED:

Any online loan application must be approved by lenders who exclusively operate online and can offer same-day funding, a capability made possible by Fintech innovation. Fintech makes it simpler to secure a payday loan or other short-term loan. You may easily receive speedy service and find a variety of lenders online. Traditional banks might not have the same benefit and it would take them months to complete the task quickly. Because fintech is a clever, efficient, convenient, and quick method, most firms choose it.

E) EFFICIENCY:

The efficiency that fintech technology can provide along with all the other obvious advantages is a benefit that is often overlooked. Fintech is renowned for increasing process efficiency. Because financial technology offers such specialized services, using it already makes you efficient. Automation offers a high degree of specialization because it doesn't involve humans. It has a high level of efficiency and service quality as a result. As a fintech company, we are capable of being both quick and flexible at once. Fintech makes it possible for you to invest in solutions for a variety of reasons, but the outcomes are clear-cut: increased productivity and better time management.

F) FINANCIAL, GOVERNANCE, RISK MANAGEMENT, AND COMPLIANCE EXPECTATIONS:

Fintech has become widely accepted by all users and is not something that is opened by an entrepreneur. The requirements and expectations for access to FDIC-insured deposits and the banking system include stable finances, effective governance, risk management, and compliance abilities that lower risks to the public safety net and potential harm to customers.

G) ADVANCED SECURITY:

Unfortunately, security is one of the main barriers to utilizing fintech. Fintech still needs to explain how it provides a high level of security despite its benefits. Remember that a single security breach, cybersecurity intrusion, or data theft puts a fintech company with less security experience one step closer to being destroyed. Smaller companies might not have the financial or human resources necessary to handle the consequences of this security incident. As a result, fintech businesses frequently spend a lot of money on their offline and online security infrastructure. Clients can therefore be confident that their information is protected.

6. ASPECTS OF FINTECH AND HOW FINTECH IS INFLUENCING THE BANKING SECTOR'S FUTURE:

- a. **GREATER CUSTOMER SATISFACTION:** The fintech industry is rediscovering the value of managing both customer satisfaction and the banking industry. Digital customer authorization is the consequence of the fusion of digital developments with customer expectations. The biggest flaw, however, is that some industry players are racing to implement outmoded customer-oriented solutions, which are not what today's customers want.
- b. **FACILITATING 24*7 CUSTOMER SERVICE:** Fintech provides the bank customer with a variety of services, such as 24/7 access, social media integration, and other online facilities. Additionally, it gives a forum for potential clients to examine and compare bank offers.
- c. **PROVIDING ROBUST SOLUTIONS TO THE CUSTOMER:** Fintech is able to offer customers in the banking industry clever and reliable solutions by comprehending their urgent and involved needs. For banks, fintech has begun extending well-defined and very successful solutions that have managed to address all the market groups that banks had previously disregarded in terms of services.
- d. **PROVIDING VALUE-ADDED SERVICES:** Through application programme interfaces, fintech is creating value-added features and solutions that are simple to integrate with bank platforms. It enables the banks to work on merging and streamlining their internal operational processes.
- e. **SUPPORT PARTNERSHIP:** Direct partnerships have emerged throughout the Fintech ecosystem as a result of rising globalisation and rivalry between banks and financial service providers.

- f. **EMERGING NEW BANKING MODELS:** By innovating and facilitating easy access to financial services for consumers, fintech is transforming the banking sector for the better.

7. FINDINGS:

1. Fintech improves the quality of traditional financial institutions by increasing efficiency and productivity.
2. The rise of FinTech and the path to digital transformation.
3. FinTech will revolution is e-banking by offering the finest customer experience underpinned by cutting-edge technology.
4. Any online loan application must be approved by lenders who exclusively operate online and can offer same-day funding, a capability made possible by Fintech innovation.
5. Fintech makes it simpler to secure a payday loan or other short-term loan.

8. SUGGESTION:

After the analysis of various studies on Fintech some points might be consider for impact & shaping the future of banks as under:

- Service Focused on the Customer
- Quick and Simple Integration
- Managing cash flow and finances
- Rapid Adaptation to Change
- Obtain money and encourage expansion

9. CONCLUSION

Fintech is flourishing and has developed a brand-new, cutting-edge method of communicating with both current and potential clients. Fintech is altering the financial sector and is governing the world, thus it is critical to adopt the technologies that are driving this change. Fintech has altered the banking industry by offering smart services, greater client connectivity, and value-added services. In order to succeed in the contemporary banking business, bankers must be innovative and have specialised expertise.

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